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PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING, GAS CHROMATOGRAPHY-MASS SPECTROMETRY AND FOURIER TRANSFORM INFRARED EVALUATIONS OF ETHANOLIC EXTRACT OF *Allium sativum*

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to identify the bioactive compounds present in the ethanolic extract of *Allium sativum* by Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) and FTIR techniques. The presence of phytochemicals in the plant were also carried out using standard procedures. The phytochemical analysis revealed the presence of flavonoid, cardenolides, cardiac glycosides, Saponins, Carbohydrates and Terpenoids. The results of GC-MS analysis revealed the total of twenty-three (23) compounds, amongst which some have been reported to be good therapeutic agents this include, cyclohexanone, 3,5-dimethoxy cis (antimicrobial), 5 hydroxymethyl furfural (antioxidant), 1-hexacosene (anti-inflammatory) and Magnesium, bis(4, N,N dimethylaminobutyl (antibacterial). The FTIR results revealed different functional groups present in the compound present in the extract, this includes alcohol, carboxylic acids, ester, alkene among others. The results study concluded that the plant has important phytochemicals of great therapeutic importance especially, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant.

Keywords: Gas Chromatography Mass Spectrometry; Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy; *Allium sativum*; Phytochemicals

INTRODUCTION

Natural products have been an integral part of ancient traditional medicine systems, e.g. Chinese, Ayurvedic and Egyptian [1]. Over the years, they have assumed a very central stage in modern civilization as natural source of chemotherapy as well as amongst scientist in search for alternative sources of drugs. According to the World Health Organization [2], a medicinal plant is any plant which in one or more of its organs, contains substances that can be used for therapeutic purposes, or which are precursors for chemo-pharmaceutical semi synthesis. Such a plant will have its parts including leaves, roots, rhizomes, stems, barks, flowers, fruits, grains or seeds, employed in the control or treatment of a disease condition and therefore contains chemical components that are medically active [3]. Phytochemicals are bio-active chemicals of plant origin. They are regarded as secondary metabolites because the plant that manufactures them may have little need for them. They are naturally synthesized in all parts of the plant body; bark, leaves stem, root, flower, fruits, seeds, etc. i.e. any part of the plant body may contain active components [4].

Allium sativum (Liliaceae), known as garlic, is a strongly aromatic bulb crop believed to originate from Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, and Western China. *Sativum* was domesticated long ago and is mentioned in ancient Egyptian, Greek, Indian, and Chinese writings. Garlic grows in temperate and tropical regions all over the world, and many cultivars have been developed to suit different climates [5]. *Sativum* is the most widely consumed bulb after onion. Almost 10 million tons of garlic are produced each year with China, Korea, India, USA, Spain, Egypt, and Turkey being the world's largest producers.

Garlic is widely used as a medicine worldwide and is regarded as an aphrodisiac . In India, garlic is used to relieve problems, such as coughs and fevers or applied externally to prevent graying of hair and to improve skin conditions, such as eczema and scabies as well as to treat tetanus and lungs inflammation. In Pakistan, garlic extract is traditionally taken orally to settle the stomach, treat coughs, and reduce. In Nepal, East Asia, and the Middle East, *A. sativum* aids in the treatment of a number of illnesses, including rheumatism, diabetes, intestinal worms, flatulence, colic, dysentery, liver disorders, facial paralysis, bronchitis, tuberculosis, and high blood pressure [5].

Garlic (*Allium sativum* L.) is one of those plants that were seriously investigated over several years and used for centuries to fight infectious diseases [6]. It belongs to family Amaryllidaceae [7]. It is a cultivated food highly regarded throughout the world. Garlic is originally from Central Asia, and as one of the earliest of cultivated plants [6]. Therapeutic use of garlic has been recognized as a potential medicinal value for thousands of years to different microorganisms. For example; antifungal, antiviral, antibacterial antihelminthic, antiseptic and anti-inflammatory properties of garlic are well documented. Moreover, garlic extracts exhibited activity against both gram negative (*E. coli*, *Salmonella* sp. and *Citrobacter*, *Enterobacter*, *Pseudomonas*, *Klebsiella* spp) and gram positive (*S. aureus*, *S. pneumonia*, *streptococcus pyrogenes*, and *Bacillus anthrax*) all of which are cause of morbidity worldwide [8].

In Africa, garlic is used as an antibiotic, and it has a reputation for lowering blood pressure and cholesterol, and inhibiting thrombus formation [5]. Leaves and bulbs are considered to have hypotensive, carminative, antiseptic, anthelmintic, diaphoretic, and expectorant properties. Spiritual uses have been assigned to garlic; in fact, it was reported that garlic could be worn, hung in windows, or rubbed on chimneys and keyholes to ward off vampires (Jaber and Al-Mossawi, 2007). It was also reported that in Islam, it is generally recommended not to eat raw garlic prior to going to the mosque, since the odor could distract other Muslims during their prayer. *Allium sativum* has been and continues to be subject of particular research interests for scientists of various fields with more than 5000 scientific publications recorded in Pubmed [9].

In Africa, particularly in Nigeria, it is used to treat abdominal discomfort, diarrhoea, otitis media and respiratory tract infections [9]. In Europe and India, it was used to treat common colds, hay fever and asthma [10]. In addition to its reputation as a healthy food, garlic has shown anti-viral, anti-bacterial, antifungal and antioxidant capacities. Additionally, anti-atherosclerotic and anti-cancer properties have also been demonstrated. Many researches had demonstrated its effectiveness and broad-spectrum antimicrobial activity against many species of bacteria, viruses, parasites, protozoan and fungi. Garlic extract inhibits the growth of Gram positive and Gram-negative bacteria, such as *Staphylococcus*, *Streptococcus*, *Micrococcus*, *Enterobacter*, *Escherichia*, *Klebsiella*, *Lactobacillus*, *Pseudomonas*, *Shigella*, *Salmonella*, *Proteus*, and *Helicobacter pylori* [11].

Compounds contained in a plant sample can be identified and determined using gas chromatography-mass spectroscopy (GC-MS) and Fourier Transform-infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR), a combined analytical approach [12]. In the phytochemical study and chemotaxonomic research of medicinal plants with physiologically active constituents,

GC-MS and infrared spectroscopy is crucial [13,14]. Thus, this research was conducted to investigate the phytochemical constituent of ethanol crude extract of *A. sativum* using FT-IR and GC-MS.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection and Identification of Sample (*Allium sativum*)

Allium sativum (Garlic) used in the present study was purchased from the local market (Tashan Bama market Maiduguri) in Borno State. The specimen was identified by Plant Taxonomist from the Department of Biological Science University of Maiduguri and was deposited in the laboratory of the Department of Pure and Applied Chemistry.

Apparatus/Instruments

The apparatus and instruments used for this study were: Beakers, conical flask (300 and 500ml), Round bottom flask (300 and 500ml), water bath, filter paper, electrical weighing balance, stirrer, mortar and pestle, Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) and Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GCMS) were used during the course of the experiments.

Chemicals and Reagents

The chemicals and reagents used for this study were: ethanol, petroleum ether (60-70%), distilled water, formic acid, magnesium chips, ethyl acetate, conc. HCl, Dragendorff's reagent, Mayer's reagent, ferric chloride (FeCl₃), acetic anhydride, conc. sulphuric acid (H₂SO₄), Iodine and chloroform. Lead ethanoate, lead acetate, Barfoed's reagent, Fehling's solution, sodium hydroxide and magnesium chips.

Preparation of Plant Extract

Allium sativum (garlic) cloves were collected from local market of Tashan Bama, Maiduguri. Bulbs of *Allium sativum* were first washed with tap water followed by distilled water and ground to fine paste using mortar and pestle under laboratory condition.

Ethanolic Extraction of *A. sativum*

The powdered material was extracted with 70% ethanol using Soxhlet apparatus. The plant material i.e. bulb was used for extraction. The soxhlet apparatus was used to exhaustively extract the plant material at 60-80°C. The extract obtained was concentrated to dryness at reduced pressure and was stored at 4°C for further analysis.

Phytochemical Screening

The phytochemical screening of the crude extract for various phytochemical constituents such as terpenoids, flavonoids, alkaloids, reducing sugars, steroids, glycosides, phenols, anthraquinones, saponins and tannins were conducted using standard methods [15-20].

Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry Analysis

The compound identification was done by comparison of retention time and mass spectra of GC-MS. In gas chromatography, heat separate the compound mixture into different individual substances and the compound was identified using the database of National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) Library 2.0. The unknown component mass spectrum has been compared with spectrum of known component of NIST library. This analysis has provided the name, molecular weight, molecular formula and area under the peak, Retention time and bioactivity of the components.

Fourier Transform Infrared (FT-IR) Spectroscopic Analysis

Fourier Transform infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopy is helpful in the identification and classification of chemical bonds/functional groups pertaining to phytochemicals. The chemical bond present in the spectrum has absorbed a light of particular wavelength. Thus, the chemical bonds present in the reported compounds can be resolved by interpreting the IR absorption spectrum. The test has been performed using Perkin Elmer Spectrum 400 FT-IR/FT-FIR spectrometer with scan range from 400 to 4000 cm⁻¹. Plant samples powder was used for analysis and different functional groups were reported.

RESULTS

Extraction Profile of Ethanolic Leaf Extract of *Allium sativum*

The result of extraction profile is presented in Table 1. The percentage yield of the crude extract was 18.6% and the weight was 150g, the texture (amorphous) and the colour is light yellow.

Phytochemical Constituents of the Ethanolic Extract of *Allium sativum*

The result of preliminary phytochemical screening of the ethanolic extract of *Allium sativum* showed the presence of cardenolides, terpenoids, cardiac glycosides, flavonoids, saponins and carbohydrates while alkaloids, anthraquinones and tannins were absent in the extract as presented in Table 2.

Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (GC-MS) Analysis

The GC-MS Chromatogram (Fig. 1) showed twenty-three different peaks indicating different components identified by the ethanolic extract of *Allium sativum*. Table 3 summarised the names of bioactive components, retention time, structure, molecular formula molecular weight, percentage peak area and the bioactivities of the identified compounds. GC-MS has provided the details account of phytoconstituents present in ethanolic extract of *Allium sativum*. The mass spectrophotometry identifies the different compound in the samples. The GC-MS disclose various compounds with relative concentration getting eluted has per the retention time. GC-MS Analysis of *Allium sativum* has resulted into twenty-three compounds at different peaks. The phytoconstituent that are reported in earlier available literature including Magnesium, bis (4-N,N dimethylaminobutyl), 4H-pyran-4-one,2,3-dihydro-3,5-dihydroxy-6-methyl, cyclohexanone, 3,5-dimethoxy-cis, 5-hydroxymethyl furfural, 1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-amine, 1-propyl, Diethyl phthalate, N-hexadecanoic acid, heptadecanoic acid, cis-11-hexadecenal, linoelaidic acid and Bis(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate.

The FTIR Spectra of Ethanolic Extract of *Allium sativum*

The IR spectral revealed different functional groups among which are ketonic group (at absorption band 1724.6 cm^{-1}), aromatic (1459.0 cm^{-1}), alkene, nitro group (2366.4 cm^{-1}), esters (1068.6 cm^{-1}), alkyl (728.8 cm^{-1}), carboxylic acid (3337.6 cm^{-1}), methyl, alkyne, alcohol among others (Table 4 and Figure 2).

Table 1: Extraction profile of the ethanolic extract of *Allium Sativum*

Parameters	Result
Weight	150
% yield	18.6
Colour	Light yellow
Texture	Amorphous powder

Table 2: Phytochemical constituents of ethanolic extract of *Allium sativum*

S/N	Chemical Test	Result
1.	Test for Alkaloids	
	i. Dragendroff's reagent	-
	ii. Mayer's reagent	-
2.	Test for Flavonoids	
	i. Shinoda's test	+
	ii. Ferric chloride	-
	iii. Lead acetate	-
	iv. Sodium hydroxide	+
3.	Test for Cardenolides	
	i. Keller Killiani	+
4.	Test for Terpenoids	+
5.	Test for Cardiac glycosides	
	i. Salkowski's test	+
	ii. Lieberman-Burchard's test	+
6.	Test for Tannins	
	i. Ferric chloride	-
	ii. Lead acetate	-
7.	Test for Saponins	
	i. Frothing test	+
8.	Test for carbohydrates	
	i. Molisch's test	+
	ii. Test for monosaccharide	-
	iii. Test for free reducing sugars (Fehling test)	-
	iv. Test for combined reducing sugar	-
	v. Test for ketoses	+
9.	Test for free anthraquinones	-
10.	Test for combined anthraquinones	-

Key: (+) = Present, (-) = Absent

Fig. 1: GC-MS chromatogram of ethanolic extract of *Allium sativum* showing different compounds at different peak

Table 3: Compounds identified in ethanolic extract of *Allium Sativum* and their bioactivities

Peak No	RT	Name of compound	Peak Area %	Molecular formula	Molecular weight	Structure of the compound	Biological Activity
1	4.454	Magnesium, bis(4,N,N dimethylaminobutyl)	0.01	C ₈ H ₁₀ N ₄ Mg	224.38		Antibacterial
2	4.854	4H-pyran-4-one,2,3 dihydroxy-6-methyl.	0.23	C ₆ H ₈ O ₄	144.1253		Antioxidant
3	5.010	Glycine, N-ethyl-n-propoxycarbonyl-ethyl ester	0.23	C ₉ H ₁₇ NO ₄	203.2356		Antioxidant
4	5.526	Cyclohexanone, 3,5-dimethoxy-cis	0.09	C ₈ H ₁₄ O ₃	158.1949		Antimicrobial
5	5.920	5-hydroxymethyl furfural	5.48	C ₆ H ₆ O ₃	126.119		Antioxidant
6	7.352	1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-amine, 1-propyl	1.22	C ₅ H ₁₀ N ₄	126.16		Antioxidant
7	7.549	Diethyl phthalate	1.52	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₄	222.24		NA

8	9.009	N-hexadecanoic acid	8.65	C ₁₆ H ₃₂ O ₂	256.44		Antioxidant
9	9.280	Heptadecanoic acid	2.20	C ₁₇ H ₃₄ O ₂	270.45		Antioxidant
10	9.538	Cis-11-hexadecenal	2.47	C ₁₆ H ₃₀ O	238.40		Antioxidant
11	9.789	N-hexadecanoic acid	7.87	C ₁₆ H ₃₂ O ₂	256.44		Antioxidant
12	10.333	9,12-octadecanodienoic acid (22)	9.63	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₂	280.45		Antioxidant
13	10.679	Linoelaidic acid	33.58	C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₂	280.45		Antioxidant
14	12..091	Bis(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate	2.81	C ₂₄ H ₃₈ O ₂	390.56		NA
15	12.213	Di-n-octyl phthalate	10.17	C ₂₄ H ₃₈ O ₄	390.55		NA
16	13.109	1,2-benzisothiazole,3-hexahydro-1H-azepin-1-yl)-1, idioxide	3.47	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S	264.343		NA

17	13.544	Linoelaidic acid	3.86	$C_{18}H_{32}O_2$	280.45		Antioxidant
18	14.175	1-Hexacosene	2.56	$C_{26}H_{52}$	364.7		Anti-inflammatory
19	14.820	Nonacosane	2.34	$C_{29}H_{60}$	408.6		Antimicrobial
20	15.974	Cyclohexane, 4-(4-ethylcyclohexyl)-1-pentyl	0.47	$C_{19}H_{34}$	262.4789		NA
21	16.476	7-pentadecyne	0.34	$C_{15}H_{30}$	210.3987		antifungal
22	17.176	Z, E-3, 13-Octadecadien-1-ol acetate	0.16	$C_{20}H_{36}O_2$	308.496		NA
23	17.529	Diethylene, 1-pentyl glycol monododecyl ether	0.65	$C_{16}H_{34}O_3$	274.439		Antibacterial

Key: NA = Not Available

Figure 2: Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectra of ethanolic extract of *Allium Sativum*

Table 4: FTIR results showing different wave number with the corresponding functional groups

S/No.	Functional group	Types of variations	Characteristics absorption (cm ⁻¹)	Intensity
1.	\equiv C-H	Bending	728.8	Strong
2.	C-H, Aromatic	Bending	785.7	Weak
3.	C-H, Aromatic	Bending	976.1	Weak, sharp
4.	C-O, ester	Stretching	1068.6	Strong, sharp, multi bands
5.	C-O, acid	Stretching	1257.4	Strong, sharp
6.	C=C, aromatic	Bending	1459.0	Medium, sharp
7.	C=C, aromatic	Stretching	1538.6	Weak, sharp, multiple bands
8.	Acylsilanes	Stretching	1641.1	Weak
9.	C=O, cyclic ketone	Stretching	1724.6	Strong, sharp
10.	C \equiv N	Stretching	2366.4	Sharp, strong
11.	S-H	Stretching	2576.6	Weak
12.	C-H, alkane	Stretching	2940.0	Sharp, strong, multiple bands
13.	O-H, carboxylic acid	Stretching	3337.6	Weak, broad

DISCUSSION

The result of extraction profile revealed that, the percentage yield of the ethanolic extract was 18.6% and the weight was one hundred and fifty (150g.) the texture (amorphous) and the colour was light yellow. From the percentage yield it has shown that the extracting solvent (ethanol) is a good solvent for extraction. The results of preliminary phytochemical screening of the ethanolic extract of *Allium sativum* showed the presence of flavonoids, cardenolides, cardiac glycosides, saponins and carbohydrates as presented in Table 2. These compounds such as saponins, tannins, steroids, flavonoids and alkaloids are known to have antibacterial activity against pathogens and could be used traditionally for therapeutic purposes [21].

Gas chromatography and mass spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis of compounds was carried out in ethanolic extract of *Allium sativum*, as shown in Table 4.3. A total of twenty-three phyto-compounds were identified (Table 4). These compounds include, magnesium, bis(4-N,N dimethylaminobutyl), 4H-pyran-4-one, 2,3 dihydroxy-6-methyl, Glycine, N-ethyl-n-propoxycarbonyl-ethyl ester, cyclohexanone, 3,5-dimethoxy-cis, 5-hydroxymethyl furfural, 1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-amine, 1-propyl, Diethyl phthalate, N-hexadecanoic acid, Heptadecanoic acid, Cis-11-hexadecenal, N-hexadecanoic acid, 9,12-octadecanodienoic acid (22), Linoelaidic acid, Bis(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate, Di-n-octyl phthalate, 1,2-benzisothiazole,3-hexahydro-1H-azepin-1-yl)-1, idioxide, Linoelaidic acid, 1-Hexacosene, Nonacosane, Cyclohexane, 4-(4-ethylcyclohexyl)-1-pentyl, 7-pentadecyne, Z, E-3, 13-Octadecadien-1-ol acetate and Diethylene, 1-pentyl glycol monododecyl ether. Among the detected compounds most of the compounds were found to be quite good therapeutic agents. For instance Magnesium, bis (4-N,N dimethylaminobutyl) which act as antibacterial agent, 4H-pyran-4-one, 2,3 dihydroxy-6-methyl (antioxidant), cyclohexanone, 3,5-dimethoxy-cis (antimicrobial) agent, and 1-hexacosene (anti-inflammatory) agent [22].

The phytochemical screening and GC-MS analysis have revealed that the ethanolic extract of *Allium sativum* has remarkable phytoconstituents of medicinal value which scientifically proven the phytomedicine of this plant in ethnomedicine as reported by El-Saber *et al.* [23].

The result of FT-IR spectroscopic study of *Allium sativum* clove identified vibrational frequencies of functional groups of different compounds in the plant samples. The FTIR spectrum of *Allium sativum* extract revealed the following class of functional groups, thus; aldehydes, alcohols, carboxylic acid, alkenes, aromatic compounds, ester and nitro compounds, which is in agreement with the report of Khyade *et al.* [24]. Different functional groups such as alkyl groups, methyl groups, alcohols, ethers were reported in the root, stem, flower and leaf tissues of *Allium sativum* by FTIR analysis [25]. Alcohol, aliphatic compounds, aldehydes, alkynes, alkenes, amines, alkyl carbonate and esters have been reported in the whole plant, of *Allium sativum* during the present study. This result is in compliance with the earlier findings except aryl sulphide, anhydrides, transition metal carbonyls and polysulphide. The variations in FTIR data are likely be due to use of different plant part or geographical variations [26].

CONCLUSION

In the present study, the phytochemical studies of the ethanolic extract of *Allium sativum* revealed chemical constituents such as flavonoids, cardenolides, cardiac glycosides, saponins and carbohydrates. Twenty-three components from ethanolic extract of *Allium sativum* were identified by GC-MS analysis. The presences of various bioactive compounds justify the use of this plant for treatment of various ailments by traditional practitioners. It could be concluded that *Allium sativum* contains various bioactive compounds which may be useful for various herbal formulation as antibacterial, antioxidant, antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory.

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